

Discovering the Emotional Appeals and Purchasing Intention on Stealth Marketing of Millennial

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Abstract:- A paradigm shift has been witnessing now in marketing communication. So many new selling strategies have been evolving which indirectly piercing in the inner consciousness of consumers while marketing a product or service. Stealth marketing is such a technique which pushes the consumers unconsciously into the marketing of a product. The purpose of this research was to analyze the impact of stealth marketing techniques on consumer purchase intention. Factor Analysis and Multiple Regression were used to examine the effects. SEM technique was deployed to model the relationship between emotional factors. The result shows that emotional and personalization factors have highest impact on the purchasing intention of the respondents. It also emphasizes to understand the emotional aspects behind purchasing decision of consumers.

Keywords:- *Stealth Marketing, Emotional Appeal, Purchasing Intention*

I. INTRODUCTION

Stealth marketing means advertising a product or a service to a person without making him realize that they are being marketed. It is a type of undercover marketing and the prime advantage of this is that it is cheaper and more attractive than any other conventional methods.

Stealth marketing can be interpreted as an innovative marketing strategy where consumers are getting marketed surreptitiously. It may be carried out in the form of discussion forums and can make a buzz by creating a positive or negative comment. Social media platforms are largely used by many companies to market their product either by the way as notifications, ads or even hash-tag forms, movies, web series, TV shows etc. can be an effective tool for stealth marketing where companies place their products somewhere between the programme which unknowingly attracts the customer and through which they can place a position of the products in their minds.

By wisely creating an atmosphere of excitement in an obtuse manner, stealth marketing attempts to introduce a new product or service line into the market. Instead of aggressively marketing the products to the entire customers, stealth marketing tends to focus occasionally to a few individuals. By the way of observing the taste and preference of selected category of customers, it loads the features of the

product to them which tends to make them a purchase decision. Viral Marketing, Celebrity Marketing, Bait-and-Tease campaigns, Marketing in Video Games etc. are the most popular techniques of stealth Marketing.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Stealth marketing can be considered as a viable alternative to conventional marketing because it is perceived more personal than traditional concept of marketing. It is more approachable technique to the marketers as it uses “emotions” and “word of mouths”. The core concept of stealth marketing lies on their unconventional method that facilitates to attract customers in an unpredictable moment at an unpredictable manner, which makes a long lasting and a memorable impact. In this study, the impact of stealth marketing on purchasing intention and its emotional appeals are incorporated.

A. Independent Variables

Personalization: Personalised services to the consumers make the business more sense. If the customers are getting personalised suggestions and recommendations they are more likely to consume it ^[1]. Personalised products contribute high level of consumer satisfaction and sustainable consumption. Stealth marketing approaches should be personalised to strike a good impact and impression on consumer’s buying intention ^[2]. Personalised marketing perceived as a positive feature which helps the consumer in different stages of consumption such as information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchased decision and post evaluation ^[3]. In this research, personalisation understood as the recognition of existing customers, personalised promotional notifications and customised page to page preference.

Hedonic Value: Hedonic value is the values which a customer receives based on his experience of fun and playfulness. As per utilitarian concept it helps consumers to solve the problems and accomplish the task. Hedonic value has a positive impact on customer satisfaction and brand loyalty ^[4]. Hedonic factors, especially; social, emotional and epistemic could influence on consumer behavior and behavioral intentions ^[5]. For the research, comfort, enjoyment, adventure and the idea were identified as the hedonic variables.

Cognitive Trust: It can be understood as the confidence of the consumer to trust on marketer's competence and reliability. Cognitive trust influences on anticipation of future interactions with the customers [6]. Cognitive trust towards a specific brand is greater when the utilitarian value of the product is high [7]. Cognitive trust contributes; reliability, dependability, accuracy, usefulness, truthfulness and credibility of the brand.

Affective Trust: It is the confidence which lies in the feelings generated by the level of care and the concern of the company demonstrates. High affective trust values lead to the greater quality assessments and purchase intentions [8]. Affective trust indirectly influences on relationship performance via the mediating variables commitment and liking [9].

Emotional Appeal: Emotional appeal had significant influences in the creation of brand value, customer satisfaction and trust among consumers [10]. A favourable emotional response leads to positive attitudes towards prefactual thinking in the form of hedonic rationalizations and greater behavioral intentions [11].

B. Dependent Variables

Purchase intention: Consumer always perceives marketing strategies with certain attitudes. The more innovative and appeals the strategies are, the greater purchase intention consumers have. Greater the purchase intention greater will be the readiness to buy by the consumers. Stealth marketing with its capricious or irregular methods for marketing, have a critical effect on buyers' purchasing intention [12].

C. Millennial

Millennial is the term first appeared in the book 'Generations' by Neil Howe and William Strauss in 1991. It was coined to describe the generational cohort of people born between 1980 and 2000 [13]. However, still there is no consensus about the exact range of birth years that constitute Millennial. In this research, Millennial in Kerala will be measured as that of those who are born from 1980 to 2000. Millennials has three characteristics which are worth considering in the research. They are (a) knowledgeable and socially educated; (b) much relies on technology [14] and social media [15] (c) and value emotions [16]. As per 2011 census, the percentage of Millennial living in the study area is 30.85% of the state population [17].

As the choice of new generation, stealth marketing methods are the most attractive tool for marketing to Millennial because of its attention-grabbing, interactive and sense of playfulness nature [18]. Humanistic, creative, customized and social media focused on marketing methods are the need for millennial as they believe one size does not fit at all. Millennial does not welcome commercials with open arms [19] and are most responsive to emotional advertising [20] highlighting the fact that to capture the attention of this group, alternatives methods rather than conventional tools should be thought of and it paves the ways for stealth marketing.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The use of stealth marketing has been increased right now because of its low cost advantage and ability to generate word-of-mouth recommendations. Increasing popularity of social platforms and virtual reality programme and TV shows, high spending time on internet to watch web series and movies, large acceptance of celebrity fan clubs and high interest on technological innovations are some of the reasons of immense growth of stealth marketing. The present study analyses how the stealth marketing reach customers does and pursue them to make a purchase decision. It also examines the emotional factors over the selection process by the millennial.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- Identify the factors affecting purchasing decision of stealth marketing by the millennial.
- Evaluate the factors of emotional attraction of stealth marketing
- Construct a SEM model of emotional attraction

V. METHODOLOGY

A. Data collection

Unit of analysis in this study was individuals in the study area. The questionnaire was carried out by online mode and focused on those who live between 1980 and 2000 in Kottayam district of Kerala. Convenient sampling method was adopted for data collection.

B. Measurement Scales

Questionnaire items were adopted from relevant previous literatures. Questionnaire items were measured on five point scale ranged from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Measurement Scales

Scale	Number of questions	Literature
Personalization	4	[21]
Hedonic Value	4	[22],[23]
Cognitive Trust	6	[24]
Emotional Appeal	8	[25],[26].
Affective Trust	4	[27].

C. Data Analysis

Data package used for analyses was SPSS 23. Questionnaire was coded, input, and screened for missing values and errors. In order to identify the relationship between variables, Exploratory Factor Analysis and Reliability Test were conducted. Statistical tools like, correlation; Chi-Square and Independent Sample test were used for analysis. AMOS 21 software has used for model representation.

To identify the patterns of relationship between variables; Principal Component Analysis was conducted. Varimax [28] rotation technique was used to clarify the relationship among factors by assuming that factors are not

correlated. Factor analysis and reliability coefficient of independent variables were described in table 2.

Table 2: Factor Analysis And Reliability Coefficient Of Independent Variables

Scale	Number of questions	Factor Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha
Personalization	Recognition of My Name	.763	.836
	Promotion Notification	.744	
	my own page preference	.711	
Hedonic Value	Comfort	.688	.769
	Enjoyment	.642	
	Adventure	.588	
	Idea	.532	
Cognitive Trust	Reliable.	.754	.774
	Dependable.	.708	
	Accurate.	.702	
	Useful.	.699	
	Truthful.	.677	
	Credible.	.585	
Emotional Appeal	Its surprises	.835	.854
	It is so curious	.812	
	Feels unique	.799	
	Highly attractive	.789	
	Newness in idea	.754	
	It s sentimental	.745	
	my favorite celebrity	.712	
	Apt product Role	.710	
Affective Trust	Funny	.687	.712
	Amusing	.655	
	Playful	.632	
	Humor	.585	

The factors comprises of Personalization, Hedonic Value, Cognitive Trust, Emotional Appeal and Affective Trust. The KMO for these six independent variables was 0.830^[29] and Bartlett's test of Sphericity (BTS) was < .05 (Sig. =.000), which assumes factorability in correlation matrix. All factor loadings ranged from .532 to .904 and Cronbach's Alpha values ranged from .712 to .854, indicates

good validity of the variables ^[30].KMO of the factor analysis of dependent variables which is described in table 4 is 0.0.814 and BTS was < .05 (Sig. =.000), which also indicates a valid factor analysis. All factors loadings ranged from .689 to .768 and Cronbach's Alpha value 0.814 showing a good validity of the variables.

Table 3: Factor Analysis And Reliability Coefficient Of Dependent Variables

Scale	Number of questions	Factor Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha
Purchase Decision	You Will Recommended	.768	.814
	You will buy	.752	
	Seek more information	.744	
	At least try	.728	
	Consider for purchase	.689	

VI. RESERACH FINDINGS

A. Descriptive Statistics

Table 4 illustrates demographic profile of the respondents. It can observe from the tables that, majority of

the respondents are 'Male' (56%). When we consider about millennial group least of the respondents (76%) belong to the age group of 35 to 40 years. Regarding Frequency of advertisements exposure, advertising leads to a high literacy of the respondents:

Table 4: Demographics of The Respondents (N=300)

Gender	F	Percentage
	Female (R ₁)	132
Male (R ₂)	168	56
Year of birth	1981-87	25
	1988-1994	35
	1995-2000	40
Frequency of advertisement Exposure	Very much (over 10 ads)	34
	Fairly much (from 7 to 10 ads)	26
	Moderate (from 3 to 7 ads)	31
	A little (from 1 to 3 ads)	6
	No exposure (0 ads)	3

B. Factors Affecting Purchasing Decision of Stealth Marketing

Table 5: Correlation Between Variables

Purchase	1	2	3	4	Decision
Personalization	.687*	1.000			
Hedonic Value	.465*	.641*	1.000		
Cognitive Trust	.477*	.824*	.532*	1.000	
Emotional Appeal	.701*	.624*	.435*	.524*	1.000
Affective Trust	.498*	.599*	.453*	.631*	.517*
Mean	3.15	3.26	3.27	3.34	3.50
SD	1.24	1.27	1.43	1.22	1.56

*.Correlation is significant at $p = .005$

The correlation and significant effect between five factors and dependent variables were shown in Table 5. The correlation signifies the impact between factors and depended variable (Purchase decision). All factors had a strong positive correlation with dependent variable (Purchase decision). It meant that a higher level of personalization, hedonic value, cognitive trust, emotional appeal, affective trust leads to a higher level of the respondents purchase decision. The strongest was the correlation between Emotional appeal and

dependent variable ($r = .701, p = .000$), whereas the least was that of Hedonic Value ($r = .465, p = .000$). ANOVA test results the regression model was a good fit for the data with $F = (5, 294) = 37.287, p < .05$ i.e factors significantly predicted the dependent variable (Purchase decision). The relationship between independent and dependent variable has been clarified through multiple regression models and results summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: Coefficient Between The Factors And Dependent Variable

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.867	.224		4.658	.002
Personalization	.173	.067	.216	1.897	.002
Hedonic Value	.015	.063	.022	3.440	.003
Cognitive Trust	.218	.023	.276	2.539	.000
Emotional Appeal	.368	.058	.403	3.138	.001
Affective Trust	.053	.074	.57	2.739	.000

All the factors affected significantly on purchasing decision conforming directly to H1 ($\beta = .173, p = .002$), H2 ($\beta = .015, p = .003$), H3 ($\beta = .218, p = .000$), H4 ($\beta = .368, p = .001$) and H5 ($\beta = .053, p = .000$). Among the dependent variables; emotional appeal contributed more to consumer decision (46.8%) which is followed by personalization

(29.3%), cognitive trust (26.8%), affective trust (22.3%) and then hedonic value (13.5%).

Following hypothesis was formulated and independent t- test had conducted to test it statistically.

H₁: Personalization positively impact on the purchasing decision
 H₂: Hedonic value positively impact on the purchasing decision
 H₃: Cognitive Trust positively impact on the purchasing decision

H₄: Emotional appeal positively impact on the purchasing decision
 H₅: Affective Trust positively impact on the purchasing decision

Table 7: Independent T-Test

Factors		N	df	t	p
Personalization	R ₁	32	98	.837	.405
	R ₂	68			
Hedonic Value	R ₁	32	98	1.619	.109
	R ₂	68			
Cognitive Trust	R ₁	32	98	-1.666	.099
	R ₂	68			
Emotional Appeal	R ₁	32	98	.664	.508
	R ₂	68			
Affective Trust	R ₁	32	98	-2.018	.046
	R ₂	68			

It can observe from table 7 that, With $p > .05$ for all variables, personalization, hedonic value, cognitive trust, emotional appeal except affective trust have same impact on the purchasing decision between respondents.

C. Emotional Attraction

Stealth marketing is using for emotional appealing to affect the consumer on a deeper level. Table 8 illustrates the emotional attraction created by stealth marketing on top of the purchasing habits of the respondents. It exhibits the psychological appeal of such type of marketing in their

minds. Eight independent variables were identified as their emotional factors and analyzed their relation with depended variable.

H₀: Emotional variables have same impact on the purchasing decision of the respondents

It can observe from table 8 that the emotional variables have same impact on the purchasing decision of the respondents ($p > .05$).

Table 8: Independent T-Test – Emotional Appeal

Emotional Appeal	Value	df	P value	Result
Its surprises	9.561	4	.049	Significant
It is so curious	8.391	4	.078	Not Significant
Feels unique	9.413	4	.052	Not Significant
Highly attractive	7.122	4	.130	Not Significant
Newness in idea	7.818	4	.098	Not Significant
It s sentimental	4.247	4	.374	Not Significant
Favourite	7.005	4	.136	Not Significant
Apt product Role	6.411	4	.171	Not Significant

VII. CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS

Structural equation modeling (SEM) was performed to test the fit between the research model and obtained data. This technique is chosen for its ability to examine a series of dependence relationships simultaneously, especially where there are direct and indirect effects among the constructs within the model. In SEM, a variety of indices are used to measure model fit. In addition to the ratio of the χ^2 statistic to its degree of freedom, with a value less than 5 indicating

acceptable fit, researchers recommended a handful of fit indices to assess model fit. These are the Goodness of Fit (GFI), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Standardized Root Mean Residual (SRMR), and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI). Following Table shows the level of acceptable fit and the fit indices for the proposed research model in this study. All values satisfied the recommended level of acceptable fit. However, the results of the normed χ^2 (χ^2 / df) value in the present study is well within the recommended $\chi^2 / df < 3$. The table 9 gives the model fit for each of the variables.

Table 9: Model Fit Indices For Cfa: Emotional Appeal

Latent Variable	Observed Variables	Regression Coefficient	C.R	P	Variance Explained (%)	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
Emotional Appeal	e1	1.000			0.631	0.844
	e2	0.810	2.211	<0.001	1.335	
	e3	2.349	3.505	<0.001	0.563	
	e4	1.964	3.187	<0.001	0.692	
	e5	1.617	3.142	<0.001	0.660	
	e6	1.957	3.230	<0.001	0.677	
	e7	2.016	2.902	<0.001	0.762	

The values got from the Confirmatory Factor Analysis have done on emotional implications indicate that the model is acceptable as the values fall within the threshold limits.

The CFA results given in the above table on the factor emotional appeals achieved satisfied all the fit indices.

Table 10: Model Fit Indices For Cfa: Emotional Appeal

	χ^2	DF	P	Normed χ^2	GFI
Recommended			>.05	<3	>0.90
Actual	12.147	10	0.275	1.215	0.969

Table 10 illustrates regression coefficients of emotional implications. All variables under the factor emotional implications have regression coefficient of more than 0.5. Therefore all of them have significant role in defining the factor emotional implications. The P values of all the Critical Ratios are less than 0.001. Value of Cronbach's alpha (0.844) shows that variables are reliable. The diagrammatic presentation of the model obtained from AMOS software is given in Figure 1.

Fig 1: CFA Model –Emotional Appeal

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VIII. CONCLUSION

Stealth marketing is the most captivate strategy as it directly influences on the inner mind of the consumers. Different forms of stealth marketing strategies can affect the emotional sphere of establishes founds significant impact of stealth marketing on consumers purchase intention. Personalization, Hedonic Value, Cognitive Trust, Emotional Appeal and Affective Trust had a positive impact on the purchase behaviour of Millennial.

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